

Spectral and equilibrium studies on some new derivatives of 4-amino-5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole

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Abstract : 4-Amino-5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (APMT), 4-(4'-methoxy)benzylideneamino-5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (PMBPMT), 4-benzylideneamino-5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (BPMT), 4-(2'-hydroxy)benzylideneamino-5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (HBPMT) and 4-amino-5-(4'-nitro)phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (ANPMT) were synthesized and characterized by elemental analyses, IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, DEPT and Mass spectral studies. Proton dissociation constants of these compounds in 70% v/v dioxan-water medium at 303 K and 0.1 M (KNO_3) ionic strength were measured. The order of the pK_a corresponding to mercapto group follows the sequence : PMBPMT > BPMT > HBPMT > APMT > ANPMT.

Keywords : 1,2,4-Triazoles, IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, DEPT, dissociation constants.

Introduction

Triazoles and their fused derivatives are reported to have diverse biological activity like fungicidal^{1,2}, bactericidal³, insecticidal⁴ and antimicrobial^{5,6}. The 1,2,4-triazole nucleus has recently been incorporated into a wide variety of therapeutically interesting drugs including H_1/H_2 histamine receptor blockers, cholinesterase active agents, CNS stimulants, anti-anxiety agents and sedatives⁷. Schiff's bases of triazole are important class of ligands and their complexing ability containing different donor atoms was reported⁸⁻¹⁰. The present study is thus planned to synthesize¹¹ a few new derivatives of 4 amino-5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole. The compounds synthesized are 4-amino-5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (APMT), 4-(4'-methoxy)benzylideneamino-5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (PMBPMT), 4-benzylideneamino-5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (BPMT), 4-(2'-hydroxy)benzylideneamino-5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (HBPMT) and 4-amino-5-(4'-nitro)phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (ANPMT) (Scheme 1). These new derivatives were characterized¹² by elemental analyses, IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, DEPT and Mass spectral studies (Tables 1 and 2). As the determination of dissociation constants of these compounds is prerequisite to understand basicity of these compounds, an attempt is also made to determine these values employing pH-metry technique^{13,14}.

Results and discussion

Spectral data :

IR spectral data corresponding to NH_2 (asym and sym), N-H, C-H, C=C, C=S and other functional group vibrations¹² in respective triazole derivatives observed is presented in Table 2. The out of plane bending vibrations of C-H characteristic of substituted benzene were also observed. Mass spectra of the triazoles showed evidence of respective $[\text{M}+23]^+$ and $[\text{M}+1]^+$ peaks (Table 2). ^1H NMR spectral data for the all triazole derivatives under study is presented in Table 3. The signals corresponding to NH and SH readily exchanged with D_2O . The ^{13}C NMR spectral data of APMT (Table 3) signify five tertiary carbons and three quaternary carbon atoms. The DEPT 45, 90 and 135 spectra recorded the signals corresponding to tertiary carbon atoms (δ 126.1, 128.02, 129.0, 130.5 and 132.01). The comparison of chemical shifts of ^{13}C NMR with DEPT 45, 90 and 135 spectra facilitated to identify the signals corresponding to quaternary carbon atoms (δ 122.8, 160.98, 178.2) in ^{13}C NMR spectrum. The ^{13}C NMR spectral data of BPMT indicate signals corresponding to aromatic tertiary and quaternary carbon atoms and azomethine carbon. The DEPT 45, 90, 135 spectra recorded signals corresponding to tertiary aromatic carbons and azomethine carbon (3°) at δ 126.19, 127.9, 128.04, 128.42, 128.6, 128.7, 128.9,

Table 1. Physical constants and analytical data

Compd.	Molecular formula	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
APMT	C ₈ H ₈ N ₄ S	202–205	70	49.01 (50.00)	4.20 (4.16)	29.06 (29.16)
ANPMT	C ₈ H ₇ N ₅ O ₂ S	199–201	55	39.75 (40.50)	2.86 (2.95)	29.42 (29.53)
BPMT	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	168–172	72	64.10 (64.28)	4.15 (4.28)	20.39 (20.00)
PMBPMT	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₄ S	201–202	75	61.48 (61.93)	4.75 (4.51)	18.21 (18.06)
HBPMT	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS	197–200	74	60.54 (60.81)	4.21 (4.05)	18.78 (18.91)

129.63, 130.4, 132.45 and 163.69 respectively. The comparison of DEPT spectra with ¹³C NMR spectrum revealed the chemical shifts of quaternary carbons (δ 125.83, 148.5, 152.20 and 162.72). The ¹³C NMR spectrum of HBPMT exhibited a complex spectrum with more number of peaks than expected indicating the compound to exist in different conformational forms (Table 3). The DEPT 45, 90 and 135 spectra recorded sixteen signals (δ 117.3, 119.93, 126.33, 128.03, 128.42, 128.8, 129.0, 129.68, 130.41, 130.84, 132.06, 132.79, 134.43, 154.37, 164.80, 166.79) contrary to the expected ten signals corresponding to nine aromatic carbon atoms (3°) and one azomethine carbon (3°). This observation further implies the existence of conformation isomerism in HBPMT. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of PMBPMT showed signals corresponding to aromatic quaternary, tertiary and azomethine (3°) and methyl (1°) carbon atoms. However the number of tertiary carbon signals displayed in the spectra is not equal to number of such atoms, which may be due to overlap of peaks. The DEPT 45, 135 spectra recorded signals corresponding to aromatic carbons (3°),

azomethine carbon (3°) and methyl (1°) carbon at δ 55.50, 114.45, 128.47, 130.41, 130.80 and 164.17. In DEPT 90 spectrum only tertiary carbon signals are recorded. The comparison of ¹³C NMR and DEPT 90 spectra with DEPT 45 and 135 clearly revealed the chemical shifts of 1°, 3° and 4° carbon atoms of PMBPMT.

Equilibrium studies :

From IR data it is evident¹¹ that the $\nu_{C=S}$ peaks in these compounds were displayed in the region of 1268–1347 cm⁻¹ and ν_{N-H} peaks in the region of 2903–3100 cm⁻¹ supporting the keto form (Scheme 2). ¹H NMR studies of all the triazole derivatives under study confirm the keto-enol tautomerism in solution form (Scheme 2). As the percentage of enol form is more, the proton dissociation from thiol group would be more pertinent with respect to proton dissociation studies. Keeping this in view, the dissociation constants of APMT, ANPMT, BPMT, HBPMT, PMBPMT were studied in 70% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at 303 K and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. All the triazoles showed one dissociable proton

Table 2. IR and Mass spectral data of compounds

Compd.	$\nu_{N-H(NH_2)}$ $\nu_{N-H(ring)}$	IR spectral analysis (ν cm ⁻¹)					Mass (m/z)	
		ν_{C-H}	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{C=C}$	$\nu_{C=S}$	$\delta C_{(OOP)}$	[M + Na] ⁺	[M + 1] ⁺
APMT	3310/3134	2934	1610	1571, 1446	1298	768, 688	215	193
ANPMT	3446/3085	2924	1603	1577, 1415	1291	962, 705	260	238
BPMT	3108	2932	1602	1570, 1483	1276	758, 680	303	281
HBPMT	2990	2937	1600	1560, 1483	1268	763, 675	319	297
PMBPMT	3109	3035, 2933	1598	1548, 1446	1264	764, 691	333	311

Table 3. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data of compounds

Compd.	δ_{ppm} (CDCl ₃)					
	1H, s, SH	1H, s, azomethine	5H, m, Ar-CH	2H, s, NH ₂	1H, s, OH	3H, s, OCH ₃
APMT	13.39	-	7.25-8.02	4.90		
ANPMT	13.70	-	7.41-7.60	5.60		
BPMT	11.51	10.06	10H, m, Ar-CH	7.25-7.96		
			9H, m, Ar-CH			
HBPMT	13.50	9.90	7.26-7.96		10.00	
PMBPMT	11.68	9.79	6.97-7.97			3.88

Compd.	δ_{ppm} (CDCl ₃ + DMSO- <i>d</i> ₆)
APMT	122.8, 126.24, 128.2, 129.05, 130.5, 132.01, 160.98 and 178.2
BPMT	125.83, 126.26, 128.04, 128.45, 128.54, 128.81, 128.96, 129.64, 130.465, 131.99, 132.455, 148.5, 152.20, 162.72 and 163.67
HBPMT	116.39, 117.41, 119.98, 122.87, 125.27, 125.83, 126.39, 128.08, 128.37, 128.50, 128.81, 128.91, 129.08, 129.73, 130.46, 130.87, 132.09, 132.86, 133.59, 134.46, 136.91, 143.39, 159.62, 164.71, 166.80 and 196.49
PMBPMT	55.53, 114.50, 125.0, 125.9, 128.47, 130.44, 130.80, 149.31, 162.77, 163.26 and 164.15

corresponding to the thiol group except HBPMT wherein a second pK_a value of OH group is observed (Table 4). The order of pK_a values corresponding to thiol proton in above systems follows the order: PMBPMT > BPMT > HBPMT > APMT > ANPMT. As the basicity is directly related to the pK_a value, it is apparent that the pK_a values are relatively low in amino compounds (APMT and ANPMT) as compared to in benzylidene amino compounds (PMBPMT, HBPMT and BPMT). This can be attributed to sp^3 hybridized nitrogen in APMT and ANPMT which would result relatively weaker hydrogen bonding with thiol hydrogen compared to sp^2 hybridized azomethine nitrogen in BPMT, HBPMT and PMBPMT. The comparison of pK_a values in two amino compounds ANPMT and APMT further reveals

Table 4. Proton dissociation constants of the compounds in 70% v/v dioxan-water medium at 303 K and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength

Compd.	pK_a (SH)	pK_a (OH)
APMT	6.388	-
ANPMT	6.213	-
BPMT	9.133	-
HBPMT	8.20	11.15
PMBPMT	9.263	-

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 5-phenyl-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole derivatives.

Scheme 2. Keto-enol tautomerism in APMT.

that APMT has higher pK_a . This may be due to presence of nitro group at *para* position of 5-phenyl group in ANPMT which is an electron withdrawing (-M effect) group that would lead to dissociation of thio proton easily than in AMPT. While in PMBPMT and BPMT, benzylidene ring influences the basicity parameter. The comparison of thiol pK_a in benzylidene derivatives reveals the order of pK_a values as : PMBPMT > BPMT > HBPMT. The higher pK_a values in PMBPMT is due to the presence of electron releasing OCH_3 group on the ring. The relatively low pK_a value in HBPMT is due to the fact that the hydrogen bonding between benzylidene nitrogen and hydroxyl group dominates over the hydrogen bonding from thiol group. The hydroxyl group in HBPMT dissociates at high pH ($pK_a = 11.15$) due to its participation in strong hydrogen bonding. From the equilibrium studies it may be concluded that the HBPMT is a dibasic acid while PMBPMT, BPMT, APMT and ANPMT are monobasic acids.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. APMT and ANPMT were synthesized¹¹ by the reported procedure¹². The synthesis of APMT and ANPMT involves 3 steps (Scheme 1(a)). (1) Preparation of phenyl carboxyhydrazide, (2) preparation of potassium salt of 3-phenyl dithiocarbazate, (3) preparation of APMT. The benzylidene derivatives viz. BPMT, PMBPMT and HBPMT were obtained by refluxing APMT with benzaldehyde, *p*-anisaldehyde and salicylaldehyde respectively in 1 : 1 molar ratio in acidified ethanol medium for 30–60 min (Scheme 1(b)). All these compounds were recrystallised from 1 : 1 ethanol-water. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC and melting points (Table 1). Elemental analyses, IR, NMR, Mass spectra were used for characterization (Tables 2, 3). IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-

Elmer 435 spectrophotometer. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra on Bruker WH (270 MHz) spectrometer, DEPT spectra on ACF 200 Bruker 200 MHz superconductivity magnet spectrometer were recorded and Mass spectra were recorded on Micro Mass VG70-70H spectrometer operating at 70 eV using direct inlet system. The equilibrium studies were carried out on a DIGISUN DI-707 pH-meter with an assembly of combined glass and calomel electrode. The dissociation constants of the compounds under study were calculated using Irving-Rossotti titration technique¹³. The experimental procedure for the titrations is same as reported elsewhere¹⁴.

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